

DYNAMIC VOLATILITY BETWEEN FOREIGN EXCHANGE RATE AND INDICES OF BSE & NSE: EVIDENCE FROM INDIAN CAPITAL MARKETS**Janamala Krishnam Raju^{#1}, Mulaka Lakshmi Priya^{*2}**^{#1}Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce and Management Studies, Adikavi Nannaya University, Tadepaligudem Campus^{#2}Research Scholar, Department of Commerce and Management Studies, Andhra Universitykr.janamala@gmail.com, priya.mulaka@gmail.com

Abstract— The present research paper analyses the casual relationship between foreign exchange rates and BSE's S& P Sensex and NSE's CNX Nifty. The linkage between exchange rate and stock market index is considered as one of the important contributors to predict and analyse the stock market of the country. This dynamic linkage between exchange rate and stock market has been analyzed considering 23 years of data from Dec 1995 to Aug 2018 using the information of monthly closing observations of the corresponding markets and Indian rupee per US dollar exchange rates. A stock index or stock market index is a measurement of the value of a section of the stock market. It is computed from the prices of selected stocks. It is a tool used by investors and financial managers to describe the market, and to compare the return on specific investments. For exchange rates determination US dollar is considered due to its international prominent role in the foreign trade. The main focus of the researchers is to find out the impact of exchange rate fluctuation on stock market volatility. Statistical tests were employed to analyze the behavior and dynamics of both the series along with time series also.

Keywords— *Foreign Exchange Rate, BSE Sensex, NSE Nifty, Foreign Trade and US Dollar*

I. INTRODUCTION

Stock market is distinguished as an extremely momentous factor of the financial sector of any economy. It plays an imperative role in the mobilization of capital in India. Stock markets are very sensitive and they get affected whenever there is any calamity in the world whether it relates to religion, politics, finance, etc. So decision in choosing the stocks for any person should be very specific. Choosing stocks should be very practical and precise and also needs to be very sure of goals in the stock market. Investors should have good idea about stock exchanges and its role in the stock market. One should also analyze the whole market before investing in any stocks because a small mistake in choosing the right stocks can leave a person bankrupt. In India there are two stock exchanges Bombay stock exchange known as BSE and National stock exchange known as NSE. BSE has 30 stocks in its group for trading whereas NSE has 50 stocks for trading. NSE stocks are also known as nifty. The record of the large companies of different sectors is maintained by Nifty which is the leading index in the Indian Stock Market. It is also known as S&P CNX Nifty, Standard & Poor's CRISIL NSE Index or simply Nifty 50. Nifty stocks consist of 23 different economic sectors.

NSE Nifty 50:

NSE provides trading facility across the nation for all securities of different sectors. Through the process of an appropriate technology, it ensures equal access to all investors in the world. NSE achieved its objectives in a very short duration. It deals with different market segments like equity market and capital market, futures and options or derivatives market, wholesale debt market, mutual funds, initial public offerings and so on. For short term investments, NSE provides the platform in the form of day trading which is most popular nowadays among the investors. Financial market in India plays prominent role on collecting money and encouraging investments, therefore, current paper is designed to find the effect of Exchange rate on Banks stock prices in India through NSE.

The outcome of this study will provide investors helps to compose their individual proper investment decisions on Banks stocks.

BSE Sensex:

The S&P BSE SENSEX (S&P Bombay Stock Exchange Sensitive Index), also called the BSE 30 or simply the SENSEX, is a free-float market-weighted stock market index of 30 well-established and financially sound companies listed on Bombay Stock Exchange. The 30 component companies which are some of the largest and most actively traded stocks are representative of various industrial sectors of the Indian economy. From the inception of 1 January 1986, the S&P BSE SENSEX is regarded as the pulse of the domestic stock markets in India. The base value of the S&P BSE SENSEX is taken as 100 on 1 April 1979 and its base year as 1978–79. On 25 July 2001 BSE launched DOLLEX-30, a dollar-linked version of S&P BSE SENSEX.

Foreign Exchange Rate:

There are a wide variety of factors which influence the exchange rate, such as interest rates, inflation, and the state of politics and the economy in each country. The exchange rate between the U.S. dollar and the Indian rupee is the ratio at which the U.S. unit of currency may be traded for the rupee. The fluctuation of exchange rate between currencies may be attributed to the economic principle of supply and demand. Speculations of foreign exchange traders about the futures of particular currencies will decide the demand for a particular currency. At the University of California, Mr. Hal Varian, a Professor of business, economics and information management, stated “As foreign exchange speculators change their views about the future, their demand for currency changes, resulting in exchange-rate fluctuations.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Divyang Patel and Nikita Kagalwala(2013) analyzed the relationship between exchange rate(\$/Rs.) and Indian stock exchange like BSE,NSE etc., using monthly data and found that there is no or little impact of exchange rate (USD/INR) on Indian stock market (Nifty and Sensex).

Deepti Gulati and Monika Kakhani(nov 2012),in their study, entitled “Relationship between Stock market and foreign exchange market in India” studied the existence of a causal relationship between foreign exchange rates and stock market by applying Granger causality test and correlation test. Study concluded that there is no or little impact of exchange rate on Indian stock market (NIFTY AND SENSEX).

According to GauravAgrawal (Dec 2010), the Nifty return and exchange rates were non-normally distributed, an inverse relationship between Nifty returns and exchange rate. Also, based on the results of Unit root test concluded that the time series, exchange rate and Nifty return are stationary at the level form itself.

The study of dynamic linkage between exchange rate and stock price of seven East Asian Countries during 1988 to 1998, by Panet al. (2007) states that before the Asian crisis, there was a bi-directional causal relationship for Hong Kong and a uni-directional causal relationship from exchange rates and stock prices for Japan, Malaysia and Thailand and from stock price to exchange rate for Korea and Singapore.

Vygodina (2006) conducted empirical study for the period 1987 to 2005 to analyze the exchange rates and stock price nexus for large cap and small cap stocks in United States. The study was made using Granger causality methodology. The results of the study showed that there is causality for large cap stocks to exchange rate but, there is no causality for small cap stocks to exchange rate.

Doonget al. (2005) conducted the study over the period 1989 to 2003 in order to investigate the dynamic relationship between stock and exchange rate for six Asian countries. From the study it is observed that financial variables are not co-integrated. The Granger Causality test was applied and the results showed the bi-directional causality between the series in Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia and Thailand. Also, a significant negative relation between the stock returns and the exchange rate for all the countries except Thailand.

Kurihara, (2006) stated that apart from exchange rate, other factors, such as enterprise performance, dividends, stock prices of other countries, gross domestic product, interest rates, current account, money supply, employment, their information etc. have an impact on daily stock prices.

Prakash G.apte (2001) made study during the period 1991-2000 to study the relationship between the volatility of the stock market and the nominal exchange rate of India using the daily closing USD/INR exchange rate, BSE 30(Sensex) and Nifty-50. In their report it is revealed that there appears to be a spill over from the foreign exchange market to the stock market but not the reverse. In recent days, economists are giving importance for the study of temporal relation between stock returns and exchange rates, for theoretical as well as empirical reasons. The development of a country's economy is influenced by the changes in the series, exchange rate and stock price. Also, the relationship between stock returns and foreign exchange rates gives the guidelines in predicting the future trends for each other by investors.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

From the literature discussed above the main focus was given to stock market and currency market as whole. In the study of Deepti Gulati and Monika Kakhani (Nov 2012), it was analyzed that the relationship of exchange rate and SENSEX is negative by showing a graphical analysis for the study period December 1995 – August 2018. Overall, the past studies concentrated on analyzing macroeconomic factors and Indian investment through different channels as a whole. The objectives of this study are as follows:

- a. To know the relationship of Exchange Rate and Sensex from the period December 1995 – August 2018 by using correlation analysis.
- b. To study the quantity of dependence of Sensex on Indian currency Exchange Rate during the period December 1995 – August 2018 by using regression analysis.
- c. To know the relationship of Exchange Rate and Nifty from the period December 1995 – August 2018 by using correlation analysis.
- d. To study the quantity of dependence of Nifty on Indian currency Exchange Rate during the period December 1995 – August 2018 by using regression analysis.
- e. To know the impact of currency fluctuation on Sensex and Nifty.

IV. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

Sources of data:

The present study is depending up on the secondary data only. The monthly data on currency fluctuations against US Dollar, Sensex and Nifty monthly average data was collected from the website of national stock exchange, money control, Yahoo finance and investing.

Sample Size:

The study has considered December 1995 to August 2018.

Tools and Techniques:

Regression Analysis

R- Square

Adjusted R square

ANOVA analysis
 Correlation analysis

Normalization technique:

The data, Currency exchange rate, is in terms of Rupees, whereas, BSE Sensex and NSE Nifty Index is in terms of points. To make these two data into equal unit of measurement, we have normalized the data. Normalization allows data of two different units of measurement to compare easily and to get relevant results. The collected data have transformed the original data of Currency value and BSE and NSE Indices ranging from December 1995 to August 2018. To create this normalization, we have used the formula as,

$$X_{\text{new}} = \frac{X - X_{\text{min}}}{X_{\text{max}} - X_{\text{min}}}$$

Where, X_{new} is the new variable created after normalization.

X is a particular value in the series of data for Currency value as well as BSE Index.

X_{min} is the minimum value of a particular series in consideration.

X_{max} is the maximum value of a particular series in consideration.

After the conversion of data, it has been analyzed the impact of normalized currency value on normalized BSE Index and NSE index. In this regard, regression analysis with these two sets of transformed variables has been applied.

V. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The data are explained in two different ways, graphically and mathematically. The two normalized dataset are plotted against the time period and the result shows that they both have increasing trends with them in long term. Figure – 1 show that as Rupee and Sensex values also have become higher over 23 years. Both the variables are moving in the uptrend direction from last 23 years. Figure – 2 shows that Rupee and Nifty fluctuations over the study period. It is observed that both the Nifty and Sensex are moving in the uptrend direction.

Figure 1: Normalized plot of Sensex and INR/\$

Figure 2: Normalized plot of Nifty and INR/\$

Table 1: Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: Market Share		Independent Variable: Year		Method Linear Regression		
Variables	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Std. Error	β_0	β_1
BSE	.816	.667	.665	.1577098	0.837	-0.058
NSE Nifty	.825	.680	.679	.1550653	0.849	-0.061

a. Dependent Variable: Normalized Sensex & Nifty

b. Predictors: (Constant), Normalized INR

Regression Equations (After Normalization): BSE

a) The linear trend forecasting equation is

$$\text{BSE Sensex} = -0.058 + 0.837 * \text{INR}/\$$$

The regression coefficients are interpreted as follows:

- The Y-intercept $\beta_0 = 0.837$ is the fitted trend value reflecting the projected mean of BSE Sensex to Indian Rupee during the study period.
- The slope $\beta_1 = -0.058$ indicates that the Sensex is projected to decrease by an average of -0.058 times. The significance value of F (0.000) is less than 0.05. Then the independent variable (Indian Rupee) is explaining the variation in the dependent variable. This table displays R squared (0.667). It is the proportion of variation in the dependent variable explained by the independent variable in the regression model.

Regression Equations (After Normalization): NSE

b) The linear trend forecasting equation is

$$\text{NSE Nifty} = -0.061 + 0.849 * \text{INR}/\$$$

The regression coefficients are interpreted as follows:

- The Y-intercept $\beta_0 = 0.849$ is the fitted trend value reflecting the projected mean of NSE Nifty to Indian Rupee during the study period.
- The slope $\beta_1 = -0.061$ indicates that the Nifty is projected to decrease by an average of -0.061 times.

The significance value of F (0.000) is less than 0.05. Then the independent variable (Indian Rupee) is explaining the variation in the dependent variable. This table displays R squared (0.680). It is the proportion of variation in the dependent variable explained by the independent variable in the regression model. It is clear from the above analysis that Sensex and Nifty are positively correlated with Indian Rupee exchange rate.

Table no 2: Analysis of Variance

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Sense x	Regression	13.478	1	13.478	541.868	.000 ^b
	Residual	6.740	271	.025		
	Total	20.218	272			
Nifty	Regression	13.862	1	13.862	576.509	.000 ^b
	Residual	6.516	271	.024		
	Total	20.379	272			

a. Dependent Variable: Normalized Sensex & Nifty

b. Predictors: (Constant), Normalized INR

From the above table, BSE Sensex and NSE Nifty have the significance values less than 0.000, it can be concluded that the data is fit to derive the conclusions about volatility between indices and foreign exchange rate.

Graph 1: Regression graph of Normalized Sensex and Indian Exchange Rate

Graph 2: Regression graph of Normalized Nifty and Indian Exchange Rate

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

For BSE Sensex:

Null (H_{A_0}) Hypothesis, here, is defined as there is no dependence of Sensex on currency value. Whereas, Alternative (H_{A_1}) Hypothesis is defined as, there is a dependence of Sensex on currency value. There result is as follows: With the transformed data, this model can explain 66.7% of the actual scenario. The coefficients are positive which ensures that the estimated regression line has a positive intercept and it is a positively sloped linear equation. Here, two coefficients are statistically significant. It can be confirmed through the p value of the respective coefficients.

As p value, in both the cases, is significant, i.e, they are less than 0.05, we reject Null hypothesis and accept alternative hypothesis stating that there is an impact of currency value on SENSEX. It is a positive effect which says that, as Rupee gets depreciated against dollar; stock market goes up and vice versa.

For NSE Nifty:

Null (H_{B_0}) Hypothesis, here, is defined as there is no dependence of Nifty on currency value. Whereas, Alternative (H_{B_1}) Hypothesis is defined as, there is a dependence of Nifty on currency value. There result is as follows: With the transformed data, this model can explain 68.0% of the actual scenario. The coefficients are positive which ensures that the estimated regression line has a positive intercept and it is a positively sloped linear equation. Here, two coefficients are statistically significant. It can be confirmed through the p value of the respective coefficients.

As p value, in both the cases, is significant, i.e, they are less than 0.05, we reject Null hypothesis and accept alternative hypothesis stating that there is an impact of currency value on Nifty. It is a positive effect which says that, as Rupee gets depreciated against dollar; stock market goes up and vice versa.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The analysis has given an importance on analyzing two time series data after taking the normalized value of two variables. The study suggests to the Indian stock investors to invest in Indian stock market for long run to get higher return and to avoid the short term fluctuation in the stock market. One of the reasons of short term fluctuation in stock market is currency value. As suggested by Purbaya, Yudhi Sadewa (2000), currency depreciation will definitely bring FDI flows in host country if host country is a primary exporter. FDI along with FII will then account for increased investment in stock market. For developing economy, if technological constraints are associated with a country, the economy faces higher amount of FDI inflows with currency depreciation. But if technological advances are there for an economy, currency depreciation will lead to less FDI inflows. Country like India, has very less exposure with technological advancement. Hence, when there is currency depreciation, it always attracts FDI to promote exports in the economy. Penetration of FDI into stock market eventually augments SENSEX in India to rise in long run.

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